

Supplementary File of “Bayesian Forward-Inverse Transfer for Multiobjective Optimization”

S-I. BENCHMARK PROBLEMS

The selected DTLZ problems are constructed based on objective functions with distance functions. The objective functions can be illustrated as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} f_1 = \frac{1}{2}x_1^s x_2^s \dots x_{M-1}^s [1 + g(\mathbf{x}_M)] \\ f_2 = \frac{1}{2}x_1^s x_2^s \dots (1 - x_{M-1}^s) [1 + g(\mathbf{x}_M)] \\ \vdots \\ f_M = \frac{1}{2}(1 - x_1^s) [1 + g(\mathbf{x}_M)] \\ x_i \in [0, 1], i = 1, 2, \dots, D \end{array} \right. \quad (\text{S-1})$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} f_1 = [1 + g(\mathbf{x}_M)] \cos(x_1^s \pi/2) \dots \cos(x_{M-1}^s \pi/2) \\ f_2 = [1 + g(\mathbf{x}_M)] \cos(x_1^s \pi/2) \dots \sin(x_{M-1}^s \pi/2) \\ \vdots \\ f_M = [1 + g(\mathbf{x}_M)] \sin(x_1^s \pi/2) \\ x_i \in [0, 1], i = 1, 2, \dots, D \end{array} \right. \quad (\text{S-2})$$

where M is the number of objectives, D is the number of dimensions, and $g(x)$ function is the distance function defined as follow:

$$g(\mathbf{x}_M) = g_a * (|\mathbf{x}_M| + \sum_{x_i \in \mathbf{x}_M} [(x_i - p_i)^2 - g_b * \cos(g_c \pi (x_i - p_i))]) \quad (\text{S-3})$$

$$g(\mathbf{x}_M) = \sum_{x_i \in \mathbf{x}_M} (x_i - p_i)^2 \quad (\text{S-4})$$

To be specific, DTLZ-1 is constructed by the objective function (S-5) and the distance function (S-3), DTLZ-2 is constructed by the objective function (S-2) and the distance function (S-4), and DTLZ-3 is constructed by the objective function (S-2) and the distance function (S-3). For the selected DTLZ problems in the original version, in distance function (S-3) the parameter set (g_a, g_b, g_c) equals $(100, 1, 20)$, while the parameter set is set as $(1, 1, 2)$ for mDTLZ-1 and $(0.1, 0.1, 2)$ for mDTLZ-3. The parameters utilized to shift the base mDTLZ problem to build multiple related mDTLZ problem sets are shown in Table S-I.

TABLE S-I
PARAMETER SETTINGS OF THE mDTLZ BENCHMARK PROBLEMS.

Task Set	Task Index	s	p_1	p_2	p_3	p_4
mDTLZ1	Task-1	0.35	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
	Task-2	0.30	0.25	0.50	0.75	1.00
	Task-3	0.25	0.125	0.25	0.375	0.50
	Task-4	0.20	0.083	0.167	0.25	0.33
mDTLZ2	Task-1	1.0	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
	Task-2	0.75	0.25	0.50	0.75	1.00
	Task-3	0.50	0.125	0.25	0.375	0.50
	Task-4	0.25	0.083	0.167	0.25	0.33
mDTLZ3	Task-1	0.20	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
	Task-2	0.18	0.25	0.50	0.75	1.00
	Task-3	0.16	0.125	0.25	0.375	0.50
	Task-4	0.14	0.083	0.167	0.25	0.33

S-II. ENGINEERING DESIGN PROBLEM

The selected engineering design problem is a multiobjective four bar truss design problem. To be specific, the objectives for this problem can be formulated as follows:

$$\begin{cases} f_1 = L(2x_1 + \sqrt{2}x_2 + \sqrt{x_3} + x_4), \\ f_2 = \frac{FL}{E} \left(\frac{2}{x_1} + \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{x_2} - \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{x_3} + \frac{2}{x_4} \right), \\ x_1, x_4 \in [a, 3a], \\ x_2, x_3 \in [\sqrt{2}a, 3a], \\ a = F/\sigma \end{cases} \quad (\text{S-5})$$

where the four variables represent the length of four bars correspondingly. The parameters are set distinctly for different task, representing the distinct operational scenarios for the four truss design problem, as shown in Table S-II.

TABLE S-II
PARAMETER SETTINGS OF THE ENGINEERING DESIGN PROBLEMS

Task Set	Task Index	F (kN)	σ (kN/cm ²)	L (cm)	E (kN/cm ²)
Four Truss Design	Task-1	10	10	200	2.0E5
	Task-2	10	8	200	1.8E5
	Task-3	8	5	200	1.5E5

S-III. HYPERPARAMETER OPTIMIZATION PROBLEMS

For all the multitask optimization cases, each single task contains a multiobjective optimization problem of hyperparameter tuning with three goals:

- *Accuracy*: In this case, all the datasets are classification problems from the OpenML benchmark [1].
- *Model RAM*: In real-world applications, it is crucial to consider model size during inference for more flexible model deployment [2].
- *Interaction Strength of Features*: In YAHPO Gym, the interaction strength of features, denoted as *IAS*, quantifies the interpretability of deployed models. Generally, *IAS* is expected to be as low as possible so that the prediction results are easier to understand [3].

S-IV. EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES

In this supplementary file, we include the additional experimental studies for more recent multiobjective Bayesian optimization algorithms including PSL-MOBO [4] and UCB-Tch [5] with advanced performance metrics, IGD⁺ and Hypervolume. To be specific, IGD⁺ [6] is a performance metric based on IGD, and it is weakly Pareto compliant. Recall that, for M -objective problems $\mathbf{F}(\cdot)$, IGD metric quantifies the convergence of multiobjective methods with obtained solution set as follows:

$$\text{IGD} = \frac{1}{N^r} \sum_{r=1}^{N^r} \min\{\mathbf{d}(\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_{opt}^{(r)}), \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}^{(1)})), \dots, \mathbf{d}(\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_{opt}^{(r)}), \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}^{(N^{nd})}))\} \quad (\text{S-6})$$

$$\mathbf{d}(\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_{opt}), \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x})) = \sqrt{\sum_{l=1}^M (\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x})_l - \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_{opt})_l)^2}$$

To inspect the weakly Pareto dominance relationship based on the IGD indicator, IGD⁺ is defined as follows:

$$\text{IGD}^+ = \frac{1}{N^r} \sum_{r=1}^{N^r} \min\{\mathbf{d}^+(\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_{opt}^{(r)}), \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}^{(1)})), \dots, \mathbf{d}^+(\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_{opt}^{(r)}), \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}^{(N^{nd})}))\} \quad (\text{S-7})$$

$$\mathbf{d}^+(\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_{opt}), \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x})) = \sqrt{\sum_{l=1}^M (\max\{\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x})_l - \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_{opt})_l, 0\})^2}$$

Moreover, we also consider comparing distinct algorithms in terms of Hypervolume [7], which is widely applied when the ground truth solution set of multiobjective optimization problem is unknown. For Hypervolume, the Nadir point in each dimension of objective space is set to 1.2.

TABLE S-III
IGD⁺ RESULTS ON BENCHMARK PROBLEMS AND REAL-WORLD PROBLEMS.

Problems	Tasks	ParEGO	PSL-MOBO	UCB-Tch	F-invTrEMO
mDTLZ-1	Task-1	0.0718 (0.0059) –	0.0601 (0.0292) ≈	0.0558 (0.0133) ≈	0.0558 (0.0060)
	Task-2	0.1542 (0.1163) ≈	0.1472 (0.0891) ≈	0.1441 (0.0968) ≈	0.1230 (0.1083)
	Task-3	0.0946 (0.0225) –	0.1270 (0.0525) –	0.1220 (0.0659) –	0.0732 (0.0167)
	Task-4	0.1309 (0.0246) –	0.2007 (0.0583) –	0.2045 (0.1518) –	0.1058 (0.0908)
mDTLZ-2	Task-1	0.1382 (0.0116) –	0.0492 (0.0064) +	0.0599 (0.0033) ≈	0.0637 (0.0050)
	Task-2	0.1839 (0.0195) –	0.1061 (0.0412) ≈	0.0873 (0.0098) ≈	0.0837 (0.0112)
	Task-3	0.2051 (0.0223) –	0.2240 (0.0272) –	0.1075 (0.0159) –	0.0797 (0.0104)
	Task-4	0.2977 (0.0283) –	0.3982 (0.0350) –	0.2489 (0.0505) –	0.1965 (0.1668)
mDTLZ-3	Task-1	0.5636 (0.0623) –	0.6303 (0.0207) –	0.5954 (0.0224) –	0.4524 (0.0119)
	Task-2	0.5818 (0.0664) –	0.6170 (0.0232) –	0.5895 (0.0741) –	0.4637 (0.0236)
	Task-3	0.5915 (0.0627) –	0.6347 (0.0227) –	0.5655 (0.0737) –	0.4473 (0.0125)
	Task-4	0.5999 (0.0490) –	0.6321 (0.0227) –	0.5825 (0.0798) –	0.4539 (0.0176)
EO	Task-1	0.0122 (0.0018) –	0.0195 (0.0067) –	0.0130 (0.0016) –	0.0079 (0.0015)
	Task-2	0.0124 (0.0020) –	0.0140 (0.0073) –	0.0126 (0.0014) –	0.0078 (0.0009)
	Task-3	0.0123 (0.0012) –	0.0149 (0.0059) –	0.0134 (0.0016) –	0.0082 (0.0015)
HPO-1	Task-1	0.0173 (0.0020) –	0.0090 (0.0021) +	0.0214 (0.0040) –	0.0154 (0.0026)
	Task-2	0.0147 (0.0020) –	0.0131 (0.0017) –	0.0144 (0.0033) –	0.0124 (0.0020)
	Task-3	0.0236 (0.0025) ≈	0.0262 (0.0081) ≈	0.0297 (0.0069) –	0.0240 (0.0028)
HPO-2	Task-1	0.0092 (0.0035) –	0.0086 (0.0014) –	0.0072 (0.0030) –	0.0056 (0.0018)
	Task-2	0.0105 (0.0024) –	0.0101 (0.0029) –	0.0087 (0.0014) –	0.0074 (0.0019)

TABLE S-IV
HYPERVOLUME RESULTS ON BENCHMARK PROBLEMS AND REAL-WORLD PROBLEMS.

Problems	Tasks	ParEGO	PSL-MOBO	UCB-Tch	F-invTrEMO
mDTLZ-1	Task-1	1.6083 (0.0193) ≈	1.5188 (0.0883) –	1.6001 (0.0352) ≈	1.6111 (0.0154)
	Task-2	1.4391 (0.1746) ≈	1.3649 (0.1733) –	1.4868 (0.1028) ≈	1.5139 (0.1529)
	Task-3	1.5439 (0.0542) –	1.3545 (0.1080) –	1.5493 (0.0480) –	1.5960 (0.0291)
	Task-4	1.4871 (0.0761) –	1.2077 (0.0928) –	1.4420 (0.1018) –	1.5632 (0.1189)
mDTLZ-2	Task-1	0.8030 (0.0287) –	1.0204 (0.0156) ≈	1.0410 (0.0106) +	1.0273 (0.0154)
	Task-2	0.6856 (0.0403) –	0.8929 (0.0663) –	0.9696 (0.0243) ≈	0.9764 (0.0281)
	Task-3	0.6888 (0.0354) –	0.7174 (0.0315) –	0.9293 (0.0409) –	0.9901 (0.0267)
	Task-4	0.5574 (0.0550) –	0.4588 (0.0480) –	0.6688 (0.0822) ≈	0.7786 (0.2547)
mDTLZ-3	Task-1	0.0997 (0.0340) –	0.0647 (0.0224) –	0.0784 (0.0370) –	0.1510 (0.0255)
	Task-2	0.0705 (0.0325) –	0.0752 (0.0153) –	0.0494 (0.0261) –	0.1394 (0.0497)
	Task-3	0.0831 (0.0439) –	0.0529 (0.0223) –	0.0568 (0.0438) –	0.1524 (0.0268)
	Task-4	0.0623 (0.0156) –	0.0618 (0.0202) –	0.0430 (0.0347) –	0.1272 (0.0365)
EO	Task-1	0.7532 (0.0026) –	0.7144 (0.0133) –	0.7501 (0.0043) –	0.7589 (0.0036)
	Task-2	0.7546 (0.0043) –	0.7297 (0.0155) –	0.7534 (0.0041) –	0.7607 (0.0033)
	Task-3	0.7579 (0.0030) –	0.7286 (0.0130) –	0.7546 (0.0046) –	0.7632 (0.0032)
HPO-1	Task-1	1.4996 (0.0054) –	1.5073 (0.0048) ≈	1.5054 (0.0054) ≈	1.5052 (0.0035)
	Task-2	1.6114 (0.0052) –	1.6159 (0.0025) –	1.6166 (0.0089) –	1.6210 (0.0046)
	Task-3	1.5377 (0.0052) –	1.5311 (0.0080) –	1.5302 (0.0146) –	1.5411 (0.0054)
HPO-2	Task-1	1.3433 (0.0060) –	1.3463 (0.0049) –	1.3477 (0.0057) –	1.3514 (0.0025)
	Task-2	1.3466 (0.0036) –	1.3468 (0.0023) –	1.3442 (0.0060) –	1.3503 (0.0029)

A. Results on IGD⁺

In Table S-III, we present a summary of the IGD⁺ (mean and standard deviation) obtained by ParEGO, PSL-MOBO, UCB-Tch and F-invTrEMO after 100 evaluations with 10 independent runs. numbers with indicators (+), (–) and (≈) imply that the compared algorithm is better than, worse than, or similar to F-invTrEMO at 95% confidence level as per the Wilcoxon signed-rank test. Notably, F-invTrEMO outperforms the other methods in terms of IGD⁺ results for 14 out of the 20 tasks, indicating a better convergence of F-invTrEMO than its two competitors. Aside from Task-1 of mDTLZ-2 and Task-1 of HPO-1 where PSL-MOBO can significantly outperform F-invTrEMO, F-invTrEMO can significantly outperform or at least functions no worse than the compared algorithms.

B. Results on Hypervolume

Table S-IV summarizes the Hypervolume (mean and standard deviation) obtained by ParEGO, PSL-MOBO, UCB-Tch and F-invTrEMO after 100 evaluations with 10 independent runs. numbers with indicators (+), (–) and (≈) imply that the compared algorithm is better than, worse than, or similar to F-invTrEMO at 95% confidence level as per the Wilcoxon signed-rank test. Notably, F-invTrEMO outperforms the other methods in terms of Hypervolume results for 14 out of the 20 tasks, indicating a better convergence of F-invTrEMO than its two competitors. Aside from one task case in mDTLZ-2 where UCB-Tch

can significantly outperform F-invTrEMO, F-invTrEMO can significantly outperform or at least functions no worse than the compared algorithms, indicating the superior convergence performance achieved by F-invTrEMO.

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